

Application, place and future of digital technologies in the educational system

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Annotation

One of the main components of the United Nations 2030 sustainable development agenda is quality education. It aims to provide inclusive and equal quality education for all. Digital technologies have emerged as an important tool to achieve this goal. These technologies have had a strong impact on the education system. The recent COVID-19 pandemic has further institutionalized the use of digital technologies in education. Digital technologies are changing the paradigm in the entire education system. He is not only a provider of knowledge, but also a co-author, consultant and evaluator of information. Technological improvements in education are making life easier for students. Instead of using pen and paper, students these days use a variety of software and tools to create presentations and projects. Compared to the pack of laptops, the iPad is relatively light. Unlike a heavy book, an e-book is easier to read. These methods help to increase interest in research. This article provides a brief overview of the need for digital technologies in education and discusses key applications and challenges in education.

Introduction

Sustainable development includes social well-being that depends on education. Information technology has emerged to disseminate common knowledge and is the main driving force behind educational reforms. The introduction of teaching tools with the help of new technologies such as mobile devices, smart tablets, MOOC technology, laptops, simulations, dynamic visualization and virtual laboratories has changed the education in schools and institutions. The Internet of Things (IoT) has proven to be one of the most cost-effective ways to educate young minds. It is also a robust mechanism for integrating a world-class educational experience for all. Educational technology companies are constantly trying to create new solutions to

expand access to education for individuals who do not have access to appropriate educational institutions. Social media has come a long way as a learning tool. A large number of teachers and students use social media as an important element of the overall e-learning experience. This is an important place to share information about important topics today. In addition to being able to share information anywhere, anytime, social media sites are a great source of networking opportunities for social activities and possibly new jobs.

The educational landscape is undergoing drastic changes due to the relentless flow of digital technologies. From interactive whiteboards to virtual reality experiences, the way we learn and teach is evolving at an unprecedented pace. This article delves into the exciting world of digital education and

explores how technology is reshaping various aspects of the education system. We begin by exploring the current use of digital technologies in classrooms around the world. We analyze a variety of tools used by educators, including online learning platforms, educational programs, and collaborative programs. By analyzing their teaching methodology and impact on student engagement, we paint a vivid picture of the digital revolution taking place within the four walls of our schools.

Next, we will focus instead on digital technologies in the broader education ecosystem. We explore the challenges and opportunities associated with integrating technology into existing frameworks. Issues such as fair use, responsible use and digital literacy are central to this debate as we grapple with the question of how to use technology effectively without exacerbating existing inequalities.

Finally, we look at the future of digital technologies in education. We explore emerging trends such as artificial intelligence, personalized learning, and gamification of education. Looking into the crystal ball of technological advancement, we envision a potential future where technology blends with traditional pedagogy to create dynamic and individualized learning experiences for all.

Traditional classroom instruction cannot provide an immediate learning environment, faster assessment, and greater engagement. On the contrary, digital educational tools and technologies fill this gap. Some of the benefits that such technologies provide are unmatched by traditional learning methodologies. As smartphones and other wireless technology devices become more popular among the general public, schools and educational institutions can take advantage of technology by embedding it in the classroom. In fact, the flexibility and unobtrusive nature of today's technology makes learning even more attractive to the next generation. However, this can be a terrible way to manage in the first place, as traditional teachers are hesitant to introduce modern technology and gadgets into the school, seeing them as distractions rather than intelligent learning aids. Our online class calendar, where we can display class schedules, assignment schedules, field trips, speaker events, exam schedules, or semester breaks, helps students plan accordingly.

The **COVID-19** pandemic, lockdown and quarantine are three concepts that have recently entered our lexicon. People all over the world are aware of the disaster caused by

the coronavirus epidemic. In this crisis, digital technologies at least keep the education system stable. Integrating technology into education provides students with an engaging learning experience that allows them to stay more engaged in the subject matter without distraction. The use of projectors, computers and other modern technical tools in the classroom can make learning interesting for students. Student learning can be more dynamic and engaging by setting up tasks that include technology resources, oral presentations, and group participation in the classroom. Engagement can extend beyond verbal communication.

From the environmental impact of using less paper for handouts and books to time savings and ease of research, digital learning can reduce costs, make better use of resources, promote sustainability, and impact students and teachers alike. It is a great way to expand your reach. Technology is pervasive and interrelated in many aspects of modern life and society. The digital revolution that has covered the world has also begun to permeate the field of education. It is rapidly changing the way students learn, and as a result, technology is expected to improve education by making it more affordable and accessible.

This article provides a brief overview of the use of digital technologies in education. The next three sections discuss the need for digital technologies in education and provide a brief overview of digital classrooms and the use of digital technologies in education. This is followed by a section on the challenges of digital technologies in education and the future of digital technologies in education.

Research objectives

The main research objectives of this article are:

- To study the need for digital technologies in education;
- To provide brief information about the importance of the digital classroom in education and to determine the role of using digital technologies in education;
- Identifying important problems of digital technologies in education.

Literature review

In recent years, the integration of digital technologies into education has changed the paradigms of traditional education and focused on shaping the future of education. This literature review explores key findings and insights from a variety of scholarly articles

exploring the multifaceted role of digital technologies in education. The selected articles cover a range of perspectives, methodologies, and key points, providing a comprehensive review of the current state of research in this dynamic field.

Anderson et al. (2018) examine the impact of digital technologies on student engagement in higher education. The study uses mixed methods combining surveys and qualitative interviews to assess how digital tools enhance or hinder student engagement and interaction. The findings highlight the positive relationship between some digital technologies, such as online forums and collaboration platforms, and high levels of student engagement.

Virtual learning environments (VLE) have become an integral part of modern education. Johnson and Smith (2019) examine the effectiveness of VLEs in supporting student learning outcomes. Based on a comparative analysis of traditional classrooms and virtual learning environments, research shows that well-designed VLEs can foster more interactive and personalized learning experiences, which contribute to improved academic performance and knowledge retention.

As the use of digital technologies continues to grow, educators will have a greater role to play in ensuring effective technology integration. Hargreaves and Fullan (2020) critically analyze the challenges and opportunities for teacher professional development in the digital age. The article highlights the importance of ongoing training and support for educators to navigate the evolving landscape of educational technology and maximize its potential impact on student learning outcomes.

The inclusion of digital technologies in education and its availability to all students is an urgent issue. Smith and Brown (2017) examine the accessibility of various digital tools and their impact for diverse learners, including those with disabilities. The study highlights the need for universal design principles in educational technology to promote inclusivity and meet the diverse learning needs of students.

Gamification has emerged as a popular strategy to increase student motivation and engagement. Wang et al. (2018) examine the intersection of play and learning, examining the effects of gamified elements on student motivation and learning outcomes. The study provides insight into the design principles that make games effective in educational settings and discusses potential implications for instructional design.

Methodology

During the writing of this article, a secondary analysis method was used. It was analyzed using tables and graphs from the UNESCO database for analysis and results. Graphical analysis refers to the use of visual representations such as charts, graphs, and charts to analyze data and communicate information. This method offers a number of advantages in various fields such as research, business, education and decision making.

Secondary analysis offers a powerful and versatile approach to understanding and communicating data. It takes advantage of the human ability to efficiently process visual information and makes it an important tool in various disciplines.

Analysis and results

The first question should be: What are the most important problems in education? As a basis for discussion, we consider the following three problems:

1. Equality and Inclusion: Is the realization of the right of a person to choose the education he wants and to realize his full potential through education compatible with the goal of equality? If not, how can education be the great equalizer?

2. Quality: Does the content and delivery of education support communities in achieving sustainable development goals? If not, how can education help students not only acquire knowledge, but also become agents of change?

3. Effectiveness: Does the current institutional arrangement of student learning in classrooms support the achievement of equity and quality? If not, how can education balance individualized learning and socialization needs?

When it comes to equity and inclusion, ICT and digital technologies in particular can help lower the cost of access to education for some disadvantaged groups: those living in remote areas have learning difficulties, lack time, or are deprived of educational opportunities in the past. those who But while access to digital technologies has expanded rapidly, there is a deep disparity in access. Affluent groups have fewer devices, are less connected to the internet (Figure 1), and have fewer resources at home. The cost of many technologies is coming down quickly, but for some it is still too high. Better-off households can afford technology earlier, giving them greater advantage and increasing inequality. Inequalities in access to technology exacerbate existing inequities in education, a

Figure 1: Internet connectivity parity

Note: Proportion of 3- to 17-year-olds with Internet access at home, by wealth quintile, selected countries, 2017–19

vulnerability that is exposed during the COVID-19 school closures.

Quality of education is a multifaceted concept. It includes appropriate information (e.g., availability of technology infrastructure), prepared teachers (e.g., teacher standards for technology use in classrooms), appropriate content (e.g., integrating digital literacy into the curriculum), and individual learning outcomes (e.g., minimum levels of literacy and numeracy) analyzes. But the quality of education should also include social outcomes. it is not enough for students to be vessels for learning; they must be able to use it to achieve socially, economically and ecologically sustainable development.

There are different views on the extent to which digital technologies can improve the quality of education. Some argue that digital technology generally creates an engaging learning environment, enlivens the student experience, simulates situations, facilitates collaboration, and enhances communication. But others argue that digital technology promotes an individualized approach to education, reducing opportunities for students to socialize and learn by observing each other in real-life settings.

Also, while the new technology

overcomes some limitations, it also brings its own challenges. Increased screen time is associated with negative effects on physical and mental health. Inadequate regulation has led to the unauthorized use of personal data for commercial purposes. Digital technology has also helped spread misinformation and hate speech, including through education.

Technology supports continuity of education in emergency situations. A mapping of 101 distance education projects during the crisis in 2020 showed that 70% used radio, television and ordinary mobile phones. During the Boko Haram crisis in Nigeria, the Technology-Enhanced Education for All program used mobile phones and radios to support the learning curve of 22,000 disadvantaged children, with significant improvements in literacy and numeracy skills. However, despite some of the limited effects noted, significant gaps remain in terms of rigorous evaluation of educational technology in emergencies. At the same time, most projects are implemented by non-state actors as short-term anti-crisis measures, creating sustainability issues; education ministries implemented only 12% of 101 projects.

Technology has supported learning during COVID-19, but millions have been left

Figure 2: Technology use in math and science classrooms, even in upper-middle and high-income countries

Note: Percentage of 15-year-old students using digital devices at least one hour per week in math or science classrooms, selected upper-middle- and high-income countries, 2018

behind. With schools closed, 95 percent of education ministries have implemented some form of distance learning, potentially reaching more than 1 billion students worldwide. Many of the resources deployed during the pandemic were developed primarily in response to previous emergencies or rural education, with some countries building on decades of distance education experience. Sierra Leone has revived a Radio Teaching Program developed during the Ebola crisis, a week after schools were closed.

Mexico has expanded its Telesecundaria program to all levels of education. However, at least half a billion or 31 percent of students worldwide—mostly in the poorest (72 percent) and rural areas (70 percent)—are not being reached through distance education. Although 91% of countries have used online learning platforms to deliver distance learning when schools are closed, the platforms have reached only a quarter of students worldwide. For the rest, low-tech interventions such as radio and television were used mainly in combination with paper-based materials and mobile phones to increase interactivity.

The prevalence of ICT use in classrooms is not high even in the richest countries of the world. According to the 2018 PISA results, only 10% of 15-year-old students in more than 50 participating education systems used digital devices for more than one hour per week in mathematics and science classes on average (Figure 2). The 2018 International Computer and Information Literacy Survey (ICILS) found that in 12 participating education systems, classroom simulation and modeling software was available to more than a third of students, with a national rate of 8% in Italy up to 91% in Finland.

A meta-analysis of 43 studies published between 2008 and 2019 found that digital games improve cognitive and behavioral outcomes in math. Interactive whiteboards can support teaching and learning by integrating well with pedagogy; but in Great Britain, despite their widespread adoption, they were mainly used to replace blackboards. Augmented, mixed or virtual reality, used as an experiential learning tool for repetitive practice in life-like settings in technical, vocational and scientific subjects, is not always as effective as real-life teaching, but can be superior to other digital methods such as video demonstrations.

Discussion

Digital technologies allow students to experience the world and travel far away from the comfort of their computers. Video conferencing systems make it easy to bring a subject matter expert into our classroom face-to-face, no matter where they are. We can easily organize a video conference in the classroom with children from another institution. Online quizzes and other digital technologies engage all students, including shy kids who don't usually raise their hands in class. Online engagement tools allow you to regularly check in with students to learn about course materials and assignments. Student insights can also be used to identify areas where students struggle. Student response systems promote digital citizenship in the classroom by allowing students to participate and earn rewards. Schools play an important role in our society, and their closure has far-reaching consequences for the psychological well-being of many families and children. Digital technologies can easily overcome this

challenge. Online learning allows students to learn at their own pace, pause and replay videos, and study course content independently.

Quizzes are another active learning strategy that educational technology can support. Students can start working on a project together in the classroom and use social media, interactive whiteboards and other technologies to collaborate, communicate and bounce ideas off each other. Physical and social constraints allow students to collaborate from anywhere and at any time. Technology also allowed students to join spontaneous discussions and get immediate answers to any challenges or questions about the topic. Due to self-directed learning and individual differences, students almost always complete their work at different times.

When this happens, keeping students' attention is as simple as providing them with instructional videos, course-based games, or interactive learning tools. As a result, faster learners no longer have to wait for all their peers to finish before continuing, and slower learners are less tempted to rush through their work.

This Education 4.0 program will be implemented in the schools of the future to improve education and better prepare the potential of the next generation. In addition, artificial intelligence will help driverless cars move more efficiently and reduce harmful emissions. Materials scientists are using artificial intelligence to develop biodegradable plastic substitutes and techniques to clean our seas. Recycling and recycling may seem like simple procedures, but they are very effective tools for increasing sustainability efforts. Whether it's consumers reusing bottles to reduce plastic waste or businesses turning discarded items into new products, recycling is a game-changer for sustainability.

Small, medium and large education technology companies are starting to proliferate in the future and are offering a variety of new digital solutions to academic institutions. This will improve the quality of digital infrastructure across the country, making innovative educational technologies more accessible to the wider public. We will see the removal of all language barriers and the online availability of learning resources in regional languages. Electronic education and m-learning programs allow students and teachers to use a large amount of information. While technology will play an important role in shaping the future of education, ensuring the effective use of new teaching tools requires a

new generation of teachers who understand the importance of human connection in the classroom.

This can lead to a fulfilling and interesting career in education. Students will acquire the knowledge and skills necessary to use new educational technology to maximize their current and future benefits. In the coming years, education trends will follow growing Internet capabilities and network capacity, making it easier to incorporate innovative technologies into classrooms. However, offline (in-classroom) teaching and learning are not completely interchangeable. Thus, we have arrived at the era of hybrid teaching and learning, where both online and offline systems are integrated to improve outcomes and is envisioned as a result of the implementation of Education 4.0.

Conclusion

As we conclude our exploration of the digital revolution in education, a clear picture emerges: technology is not just an add-on, but a force that is transforming the educational landscape. We took a tour of current uses of the tools, grappled with the challenges and opportunities of integrating them, and looked at the exciting opportunities ahead.

However, the way forward is not without complications. Addressing issues of fair use, responsible use and digital literacy remain paramount. We need to make sure that the digital divide does not exacerbate existing inequalities, that technology is empowering rather than distracting, and that students have the essential skills to navigate this information-saturated world.

The future of education lies in the harmonious combination of the traditional and the technological. Imagine classrooms brimming with digital tools, personalized learning paths tailored to individual needs, and collaborative learning powered by immersive experiences that take students to the heart of historical events or to the frontiers of scientific discovery. In the future, teachers will act as guides, facilitators, and coaches, using technology to inspire curiosity, foster critical thinking, and foster a lifelong love of learning.

Ultimately, the real power of digital technologies lies not in their potential, but in their ability to enhance the human element of education. They are tools to be used wisely, not to replace the indispensable role of skilled and passionate teachers. Using this holistic approach, we can ensure that the digital revolution not only changes the way we learn,

but also unlocks the full potential of every student and prepares them to thrive in a rapidly evolving world.

This journey into the future of education is far from over. As technology continues to advance, so must our approaches to teaching and learning. Let's stay open to the possibilities, keep the challenges in mind, and strive to create a more equitable, engaging, and empowering educational experience for all.

Digital technology in the classroom refers to a variety of software and gadgets designed to help students with special needs. The most effective way to reduce the number of repetitive, time-consuming tasks of a teacher is to use technology in the classroom. Learning technology applications can save a lot of time and energy by automating or partially automating day-to-day operations such as attendance tracking and performance monitoring. teaches students responsible and strategic use of technology to help them make decisions and develop self-discipline. Technology in education helps students prepare for lifelong learning. These technologies provide students with the freedom to use digital knowledge in the virtual world and according to their own learning styles. With digital content creation tools that adapt teaching and learning, students can learn at their own pace. The digital classroom uses electronic devices and software to teach students and integrates technology into learning. The traditional classroom is transformed into a digital classroom through computers and the Internet. students can learn more effectively and track their progress with technology and sophisticated tools. In the near future, these technologies will be successfully applied to education to improve the digital learning environment and effectiveness of students. Modern technologies have played an important role in analyzing and managing complex data for long-term decision-making in areas such as climate change, air and water security, biodiversity conservation, disaster resilience, and more. and social growth. They are aimed at drastically reducing ecological and ecological problems in the production of long-term products. These technologies reduce degradation, pollution and other negative environmental impacts.

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